

1983 in Guangdong Province, China. Eight plant species grown in pots were confined with 1-5 viruliferous zigzag leafhoppers *Recilia dorsalis* Motsch per plant until the vector died (34 d). Maize plants also were inoculated with green leafhopper *Nephotettix cincticeps*. Disease symptoms developed 15-25 d after inoculation. Plants without symptoms were observed for 5-6 mo.

GDV infected wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), oat (*Avena sativa*), wild rice (*Oryza rufipogon*), Japanese grass (*Alopecurus aequalis*), and maize (*Zea mays*). Small galls developed on field grass (*Leptochloa chinensis*), but further confirmation is needed. *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Leersia hexandra* did not have virus symptoms (see table).

Maize is a new host of GDV. Both zigzag and green leafhoppers

Host range of GDV in Guangdong, China, 1983.^a

Host	Zigzag leafhopper per plant	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	1	17	2
<i>Avena sativa</i>	1	15	3
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	4	6	3
<i>Alopecurus aequalis</i>	5	3	2
	3	12	1
<i>Zea mays</i>	7	5	1
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	3	5	small galls
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	3	5	0
	3	5	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	1	15	0

^a*Nephotettix cincticeps* were used to inoculate the virus.

transmitted GDV to maize. Symptoms developed 28 d after inoculation. Small, light green galls appeared on the leaf veins, enlarged, and became waxy white. Some galls formed vein swellings up to

1.5 cm long and 0.25 cm wide. Stunting was not serious. The results were confirmed when rice plants exhibited typical symptoms after back-inoculation. *ℵ*

Rice diseases on the Godavari Delta

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We surveyed rice disease status in 1983 rabi, 1984 kharif, and 1984 rabi in East

and West Godavari Districts. Surveyors visited 69 villages and talked with 86 farmers in West Godavari, and visited 31 villages and talked with 35 farmers in East Godavari.

- Blast (BI), which only occurs in rabi, sheath blight (ShB), and

bacterial blight were major diseases, and caused substantial yield losses.

- Tungro (RTV) occurs sporadically, but southern coastal districts had RTV epidemics in 1984 kharif.
- IR50 is highly susceptible to BI. Applying heavy N doses (60-140 kg N/ha) increased BI disease seventy. Rabi varieties BPT1235 and IR62 have BI resistance (see table).
- Stem rot caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, brown spot caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and sheath rot caused by *Acrocyldrium oryzae* were sometimes observed, but caused negligible losses. *ℵ*

Disease incidence^a on different rices in Andhra Pradesh, India, 1983-84.

Variety	Disease incidence				
	Bacterial blight	Blast	Tungro	Sheath blight	Stem rot
			<i>Rabi</i>		
IR50	–	VS	–	M	–
IET1444	M	–	S	–	SL
BPT1235	SL	SL	M	S	–
IR62	–	M	–	S	–
RP6-17	–	SL	M	–	SL
Prabhat	–	–	SL	–	–
IR36	–	M	–	–	–
Mahsuri	–	–	–	–	–
MTU5 249	–	–	–	M	–
			<i>Kharif</i>		
MTU7029	SL	–	–	S	–
MTU5249	–	–	–	–	M
MTU4870	–	–	–	M	–
MTU2077	M	–	–	M	–
MTU2067	M	–	–	M	–
RP6-17	–	–	–	M	–
MTU6024	SL	–	–	M	–
IR42	SL	–	–	–	–
Jaya	SL	–	–	–	–
Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
Swarna Mahsuri	SL	–	–	–	–
IR62	M	–	–	S	–

^a SL = slight, M = moderate, S = severe, VS = very severe.

BR3 reaction to multiple disease infection

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Rice fields often are infected by more than one disease. We evaluated BR3 under multiple disease infection. BR3 seedlings were transplanted in 48 rows of 10 hills each. The field received the recommended 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha.

Table 1. Disease index of four diseases and their interaction on BR3 in 1984 aus, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Inoculant	Average disease index ^a							
	BB		ShB		ShR		LSc	
	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB
0	3.67 d A	2.67 b A	2.67 a B	3.33 e A	0.67 f A	0.33 d A	3.67 d A	2.67 c A
2 (ShR)	2.67 d A	3.00 b A	0.0 c B	5.00 cd A	4.33 b A	4.33 ab A	2.33 e A	3.00 bc A
3 (BB)	6.33 a A	3.00 b B	1.67 ab B	5.00 cd A	2.33 cd A	1.67 c A	5.00 c A	2.67 c B
4 (LSc)	3.00 d A	3.00 b A	0.33 c B	4.33 de A	1.00 ef A	2.00 c A	5.33 bc A	5.00 a A
2, 3	5.00 b A	6.00 a A	0.0 c B	6.33 a A	3.00 c A	3.67 b A	3.67 d A	2.67 c A
2, 4	4.33 c A	2.33 b B	0.0 c B	5.33 bc A	2.67 c A	3.67 b A	5.00 c A	3.67 b B
3, 4	5.00 b A	2.33 b B	0.33 c B	5.83 ab A	1.67 de A	1.67 c A	6.67 a A	5.00 a B
2, 3, 4	5.00 b A	5.33 a A	1.00 b B	6.00 ab A	5.67 a A	4.67 a A	6.00 b A	5.00 a A

^aData are averages of 3 figures based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*. 0 = no disease inoculation, 2 = ShR, 3 = BB, and 4 = LSc. Small letters in a column indicate differences among treatments. Capital letters in a row indicate difference with and without ShB.

Table 2. F values of yield characters of BR3 with multiple disease infection, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.^a

SV	F values		
	Fertile tiller (%)	Filled grain (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Multiple infection	2.01 ^{ns}	1.08 ^{ns}	2.13 ^{ns}
No disease vs ShB	12.38**	19.81**	14.54**
Multiple infection × no disease vs ShB	2.12 ^{ns}	1.07 ^{ns}	2.09 ^{ns}
CV %	10.63	11.07	4.11

^aDiseases were ShB, ShR, BB, and LSc. ns = insignificant F value; ** = 1% significant F value.

Plots were inoculated with one to four diseases using a completely randomized design. Subplots were sheath blight (ShB) and no ShB inoculation. Plants were inoculated with ShB and bacterial blight (BB) inocula at maximum tillering, and with sheath rot (ShR) and leaf scald (LSc) at flag leaf stage.

Reactions were significantly different among treatments and with and without ShB (Table I). When LSc infection was high, BB infection was lower. ShB was highest in ShB-inoculated plants and

suppressed the other diseases. ShR was high only when alone, with ShB inoculation, or with inoculation of all diseases. It appeared that ShB did not affect ShR development.

Only ShB was significantly and negatively correlated with fertile tillers, number of filled grains, and 1,000-grain weight ($r = -0.60^*$, -0.81^{**} , and -0.58^*). Of the four diseases, ShB developed fastest and caused the most damage. Values for yield component characters are in Table 2. *ℒ*

Sheath blight (ShB) control

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ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk is a serious rice disease in Kerala. Under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, we evaluated different fungicides for ShB control in a field trial with 1R50. There were seven treatments with four replications in a randomized block design. Plants were inoculated 25 d after planting with ShB pathogen that was multiplied on unhusked rice grains. Fungicides were sprayed 40 and 50 d after planting. Disease incidence and

Chemical control of ShB in 1984-85 kharif, Pattambi, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	Disease incidence (%)	Disease severity (0-9)
Carbendazim 50 WP (Bavistin)	500 g	29 (31)	3
Carbendazim 50 WP (Jkstein)	500 g	24 (29)	2
Thiophanate 70 WP	500 g	30 (33)	2
Mancozeb 75 WP	1250 g	37 (38)	4
Validamycin 3L	1000 ml	13 (21)	1
IBP 48 EC	500 ml	343 (36)	
Check (unsprayed)	—	81 (65)	9
CD (0.05)		(11)	1
CV (%)		19	21

severity were measured by counting infected tillers from 10 randomly selected hills from each plot and scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All the fungicides checked ShB intensity (see table). Validamycin 3L at 1 litre/ha and carbendazim 500 g/ha performed similarly and significantly better than other treatments (see table). *ℒ*

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